

Utilization of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem based on Matrix Approach in Computation of the Power of Base of Tri-Digits Number

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Abstract—The use of binomial theorem to expand trinomial expression of particular power n requires a bit by bit breaking down of the expansion until the final answer is obtained. This method had been seen not direct enough and involve repeated application up to the final results is achieved which make the method to be unattractive. There is need to develop a direct and straight way expanding trinomial expression of any power. This study utilized kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix approach in computation of the power of base of tri-digits number. This method adopts and employs kif matrix approach in generating the power combination required in the evaluation. This method would help to eliminate humdrum nature of using binomial theorem in expanding trinomial expression of any power.

Keywords— tri-digits number, kif trinomial theorem, binomial theorem, power of base number, kif matrix approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

The binomial theorem is generally and commonly used to expand binomial expression of power of n . The theorem cannot be used to expand trinomial or multinomial expression of a particular power directly or in a straight forward way [1]. The process of doing that is cumbersome, complicated and tedious which can lead to loss of focus for large power of n [2, 3].

Trinomial expansion theorem is a theorem which helps to give long expression terms without involving any two or more terms of the expression enclosed with power. Mestrovic (2018) and Kataria (2016) indicate that trinomial theorem has many applications in combinatorics, statistics, number theory and computing. Binomial and trinomial represent a special kind of polynomials [5]. Osanyinpeju (2020) developed Kifilideen trinomial theorem using matrix approach.

This Kifilideen trinomial theorem enables all the terms of the expansion of trinomial expression of power of n to be generated with easy and allow accurate prediction of the trinomial coefficients and any term produce in the trinomial expansion of a very large power of n to be obtainable without any difficulty [6].

The kifilideen trinomial theorem helps to expand trinomial expression of a given power in a periodicity and orderly manner which straightforward procedure using matrix approach [6]. The expansion of trinomial expression of power of n is done by

first developing the kif matrix of the trinomial expression of the power of n then the evaluated terms of each row is added together. The single column matrix obtained is further simplified to achieve the final answer.

The kif matrix approach in solving the trinomial expression of power n does not involve the repeated multiplication of figure unlike the long multiplication approach. This eliminates the boring nature of using binomial theorem to expand trinomial of power n .

The used of binomial theorem to expand trinomial expression of particular power n required a bit by bit breaking down of the expansion until the final answer is obtained. This method had been seen not direct enough and involve repeated application up to the final results is achieved. There need to develop a direct and straight way expanding trinomial expression of any power. Osanyinpeju (2019) established kif matrix method of multiplication in the computation of power of base 11 and $abcd \times (11)^n$. It was indicated that this procedure can be extended to other power of base of di-digits number [8]. Osanyinpeju (2020) developed matrix approach in computation of power of base of di-digits number. This study utilized kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix approach in computation of the power of base of tri-digits number.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Expansion of power of trinomial expansion

The expansion of the power of trinomial expansion can be carried out directly using kifilideen trinomial theorem

B. Illustration in the expansion of power of trinomial expansion

[i] Evaluate the amount of money accumulated after 3 years when \$1 is deposited in a bank paying an annual interest rate of 26 %, compounded yearly using kif trinomial theorem. of a compound 1.26^3 using kif trinomial theorem.

Solution

Amount of money accumulated = $P \left(1 + \frac{R}{100}\right)^T$ (1)

From the question, P = \$1, R = 26 % and T = 3 years

Amount of money accumulated = $1 \left(1 + \frac{26}{100}\right)^3$ (2)

Amount of money accumulated = 1.26^3 (3)

Amount of money accumulated = $[1 + 0.2 + 0.06]^3$ (4)

The combination power for the expansion of the trinomial expression of power 3 in ascending order of terms are 300, 210, 120, 030, 201, 111, 021, 102, 012 and 003

$$1.26^3 = [1 + 0.2 + 0.06]^3 = {}_{3,0,0}C_3 1^3 0.2^0 0.06^0 + {}_{2,1,0}C_3 1^2 0.2^1 0.06^0 + {}_{1,2,0}C_3 1^1 0.2^2 0.06^0 + {}_{0,3,0}C_3 1^0 0.2^3 0.06^0 + {}_{2,0,1}C_3 1^2 0.2^0 0.06^1 + {}_{1,1,1}C_3 1^1 0.2^1 0.06^1 + {}_{0,2,1}C_3 1^0 0.2^2 0.06^1 + {}_{1,0,2}C_3 1^1 0.2^0 0.06^2 + {}_{0,1,2}C_3 1^0 0.2^1 0.06^2 + {}_{0,0,3}C_3 1^0 0.2^0 0.06^3$$
 (5)

$$1.26^3 = 1 + 0.6 + 0.12 + 0.008 + 0.18 + 0.072 + 0.0072 + 0.0108 + 0.00216 + 0.000216$$
 (6)

$$1.26^3 = 2.000376$$
 (7)

[ii] Expand in the power of x $[3 - x + 2x^2]^5$ using kif trinomial theorem. If $3 - x + 2x^2 = 2.895$ hence evaluate $[2.895]^5$.

Solution

The combination power for the expansion of the trinomial expression of power 5 in ascending order of terms are 500, 410, 320, 230, 140, 050, 401, 311, 221, 131, 041, 302, 212, 122, 032, 203, 113, 023, 104, 014 and 005.

$$[3 - x + 2x^2]^5 = {}_{5,0,0}C_5 (3)^5 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{4,1,0}C_5 (3)^4 (-x)^1 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{3,2,0}C_5 (3)^3 (-x)^2 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{2,3,0}C_5 (3)^2 (-x)^3 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{1,4,0}C_5 (3)^1 (-x)^4 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{0,5,0}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^5 (2x^2)^0 + {}_{4,0,1}C_5 (3)^4 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^1 + {}_{3,1,1}C_5 (3)^3 (-x)^1 (2x^2)^1 + {}_{2,2,1}C_5 (3)^2 (-x)^2 (2x^2)^1 + {}_{1,3,1}C_5 (3)^1 (-x)^3 (2x^2)^1 + {}_{0,4,1}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^4 (2x^2)^1 + {}_{3,0,2}C_5 (3)^3 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^2 + {}_{2,1,2}C_5 (3)^2 (-x)^1 (2x^2)^2 + {}_{1,2,2}C_5 (3)^1 (-x)^2 (2x^2)^2 + {}_{0,3,2}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^3 (2x^2)^2 + {}_{2,0,3}C_5 (3)^2 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^3 + {}_{1,1,3}C_5 (3)^1 (-x)^1 (2x^2)^3 + {}_{0,2,3}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^2 (2x^2)^3 + {}_{1,0,4}C_5 (3)^1 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^4 + {}_{0,1,4}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^1 (2x^2)^4 + {}_{0,0,5}C_5 (3)^0 (-x)^0 (2x^2)^5$$
 (8)

$$[3 - x + 2x^2]^5 = 243 - 405x + 270x^2 - 90x^3 + 15x^4 - x^5 + 810x^2 - 1080x^3 + 540x^4 - 120x^5 + 10x^6 + 1080x^4 - 1080x^5 + 360x^6 - 40x^7 + 720x^6 - 480x^7 + 80x^8 + 240x^8 - 80x^9 + 32x^{10}$$
 (9)

$$[3 - x + 2x^2]^5 = 243 - [405]x + [270 + 810]x^2 + [-90 - 1080]x^3 + [15 + 540 + 1080]x^4 + [-1 - 120 - 1080]x^5 + [10 + 360 + 720]x^6 + [-40 - 480]x^7 + [80 + 240]x^8 + [-80]x^9 + [32]x^{10}$$
 (10)

$$[3 - x + 2x^2]^5 = 243 - 405x + 1080x^2 - 1170x^3 + 1635x^4 - 1201x^5 + 1090x^6 - 520x^7 + 320x^8 - 80x^9 + 32x^{10}$$
 (11)

$$[b] 3 - x + 2x^2 = 2.895 = 3 - 0.105$$
 (12)

$$\text{So, } -x + 2x^2 = -0.105$$
 (13)

$$2x^2 - x + 0.105 = 0$$
 (14)

$$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$
 (15)

$$a = 2, b = -1 \text{ and } c = 0.105$$
 (16)

$$x = \frac{-[-1] \pm \sqrt{[-1]^2 - 4 \times 2 \times 0.105}}{2 \times 2}$$
 (17)

$$x = \frac{1 \pm 0.4}{4}$$
 (18)

$$x = 0.35 \text{ or } 0.15$$
 (19)

$$\text{from, } [3 - x + 2x^2]^5 = 243 + 405x + 1080x^2 - 1170x^3 + 1635x^4 - 1201x^5 + 1090x^6 - 520x^7 + 320x^8 - 80x^9 + 32x^{10}$$
 (20)

$$[2.895]^5 = 243 - 405 [0.35] + 1080 [0.35]^2 - 1170 [0.35]^3 + 1635 [0.35]^4 - 1201 [0.35]^5 + 1090 [0.35]^6 - 520 [0.35]^7 + 320 [0.35]^8 - 80 [0.35]^9 + 32 [0.35]^{10}$$
 (21)

$$[2.895]^5 = 203.3493742$$
 (22)

[iii] In the expansion of $[3 - x + ax^2]^5$ and in the simplification of the terms generate, one of the term has an expression of $1080x^2$. Determine the possible value of a.

Solution

The general expression of any of the terms of the kif trinomial expansion of the expression

$$[3 - x + ax^2]^5 \text{ is } {}_{r,s,t}C_5 (3)^r (-x)^s (ax^2)^t$$
 (23)

$${}_{r,s,t}C_5 (3)^r (-1)^s (x)^s (a)^t (x^2)^t$$
 (24)

$${}_{r,s,t}C_5 (3)^r (-1)^s (a)^t (x)^{s+2t}$$
 (25)

Comparing (25) with $1080x^2$, we have

$$s + 2t = 2$$
 (26)

$$\text{Also, } r + s + t = 5$$
 (27)

Note since s and t are parts of the power combination. The possible values of s and t are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.

$$\text{For } t = 0, s + 2t = 2$$
 (28)

$$s = 2$$
 (29)

$$r + s + t = 5$$
 (30)

$$r + 2 + 0 = 5$$
 (31)

$$r = 3$$
 (32)

So, for $t = 0$ the power combination is 320.

$$\text{For } t = 1, s + 2t = 2$$
 (33)

$$s = 0$$
 (34)

$$r + s + t = 5$$
 (35)

$$r + 0 + 1 = 5$$
 (36)

$$r = 4$$
 (37)

Moreover, $t \neq 2$ or have higher value since it would make the value of s to be negative in equation [4]. So, the power

combinations that would generate the simplified term of expression $1080x^2$ are 320 and 401. Both 320 and 401 are in row three in the kif matrix for power of 5.

So, for $t = 1$ the power combination is 401.

$${}_{3,2,0}^5C(3)^r(-1)^s(a)^t(x)^{s+2t} + {}_{4,0,1}^5C(3)^r(-1)^s(a)^t(x)^{s+2t} = 1080x^2 \quad (38)$$

$${}_{3,2,0}^5C(3)^3(-1)^2(a)^0(x)^{2+2 \times 0} + {}_{4,0,1}^5C(3)^4(-1)^0(a)^1(x)^{0+2 \times 1} = 1080x^2 \quad (39)$$

$$270(x)^2 + 405(a)^1(x)^2 = 1080x^2 \quad (40)$$

$$405a = 1080 - 270 = 810 \quad (41)$$

$$a = 2 \quad (42)$$

[iv] Find the coefficient of x^3 in the expansion of $[2 + x + 3x^2]^6$

Solution

The general expression of any of the terms of the kif trinomial expansion of the expression $[2 + x + 3x^2]^6$ is

$${}_{r,s,t}^6C(2)^r(x)^s(3x^2)^t \quad (43)$$

$${}_{r,s,t}^6C(2)^r(x)^s(3)^t(x^2)^t \quad (44)$$

$${}_{r,s,t}^6C(2)^r(3)^t(x)^{s+2t} \quad (45)$$

Let the terms with x^3 be ax^3

Comparing (45) with ax^3 , we have

$$s + 2t = 3 \quad (46)$$

$$\text{Also, } r + s + t = 6 \quad (47)$$

Note since s and t are parts of the power combination. The possible values of s and t are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6.

$$\text{For } t = 0, \quad s + 2t = 3 \quad (48)$$

$$s = 3 \quad (49)$$

$$r + s + t = 6 \quad (50)$$

$$r + 3 + 0 = 6 \quad (51)$$

$$r = 3 \quad (52)$$

So, for $t = 0$ the power combination is 330.

$$\text{For } t = 1, \quad s + 2t = 3 \quad (53)$$

$$s = 1 \quad (54)$$

$$r + s + t = 6 \quad (55)$$

$$r + 1 + 1 = 6 \quad (56)$$

$$r = 4 \quad (57)$$

So, for $t = 1$ the power combination is 411.

$$\text{For } t = 2, \quad s + 2t = 3 \quad (58)$$

$$s = 1 \quad (59)$$

$$r + s + t = 6 \quad (60)$$

$$r + 1 + 1 = 6 \quad (61)$$

$$r = 4 \quad (62)$$

Moreover, $t \neq 2$ or have higher value since it would make the value of s to be negative in equation [4]. So, the power

combinations that would generate the simplified term of expression ax^3 are 330 and 411. Both 330 and 411 power combinations present in row four in the kif matrix for power of 6.

$${}_{3,3,0}^6C(2)^r(3)^t(x)^{s+2t} + {}_{4,1,1}^6C(2)^r(3)^t(x)^{s+2t} = ax^3 \quad (63)$$

$${}_{3,3,0}^6C(2)^3(3)^0(x)^{3+2 \times 0} + {}_{4,1,1}^6C(2)^4(3)^1(x)^{1+2 \times 1} = ax^2 \quad (64)$$

$$160(x)^3 + 1440(x)^3 = 1600x^3 \quad (65)$$

The coefficient of x^3 in the expansion of $[2 + x + 3x^2]^6$ is 1600

[v] Find the coefficient of x^{-9} in the expansion of

$$\left[1 + \frac{x^2}{y^3} + \frac{yz^2}{x^3}\right]^8$$

Solution

The general expression of any of the terms of the kif trinomial expansion of the expression

$$\left[1 + \frac{x^2}{y^3} + \frac{yz^2}{x^3}\right]^8 \text{ is}$$

$${}_{r,s,t}^8C(1)^r\left(\frac{x^2}{y^3}\right)^s\left(\frac{yz^2}{x^3}\right)^t \quad (66)$$

$${}_{r,s,t}^8C(1)^r(x^2)^s(y^{-3})^s(y)^t(z^2)^t(x^{-3})^t \quad (67)$$

$${}_{r,s,t}^8C(1)^r(x)^{2s-3t}(y)^{-3s+t}(z)^{2t} \quad (68)$$

Let the terms with x^{-9} be ax^{-9}

Comparing (68) with ax^{-9} , we have

$$2s - 3t = -9 \quad (69)$$

$$\text{Also, } r + s + t = 8 \quad (70)$$

Note since s and t are parts of the power combination. The possible values of s and t are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8.

For $t = 0, 4, 6$ and 8 the values of s are fraction which is not possible.

For $t = 1$ and 2 the values of s are negative which is not possible.

$$\text{So, for } t = 3 \quad 2s - 3t = -9 \quad (71)$$

$$s = 0 \quad (72)$$

$$r + s + t = 8 \quad (73)$$

$$r + 0 + 3 = 8 \quad (74)$$

$$r = 5 \quad (75)$$

Therefore, for $t = 3$ the power combination is 503

$$\text{For } t = 5, \quad 2s - 3t = -9 \quad (76)$$

$$s = 3 \quad (77)$$

$$r + s + t = 8 \quad (78)$$

$$r + 3 + 5 = 8 \quad (79)$$

$$r = 0 \quad (80)$$

So, for $t = 5$ the power combination is 035.

For $t = 7,$

$$(234)^2 = 54356 \text{ or } 5.4756 \times 10^4 \quad (92)$$

[ii] $(875)^2$

The kifilideen matrix to solve the expression is given has

$$\begin{bmatrix} 200 \\ 110 \\ 020 + 101 \\ 011 \\ 002 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, we have

$$(875)^2 = \begin{bmatrix} {}_{2,0,0}^2C 8^2 7^0 5^0 \\ {}_{1,1,0}^2C 8^1 7^1 5^0 \\ {}_{0,2,0}^2C 8^0 7^2 5^0 + {}_{1,0,1}^2C 8^1 7^0 5^1 \\ \phantom{{}_{0,2,0}^2C 8^0 7^2 5^0} + {}_{0,1,1}^2C 8^0 7^1 5^1 \\ \phantom{{}_{0,2,0}^2C 8^0 7^2 5^0} \phantom{+ {}_{1,0,1}^2C 8^1 7^0 5^1} + {}_{0,0,2}^2C 8^0 7^0 5^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (93)$$

$$(875)^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 64 \\ 112 \\ 49 + 80 \\ 70 \\ 25 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 64 \\ 112 \\ 129 \\ 70 \\ 25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (94)$$

$$(875)^2 = 765625 \text{ or } 7.65625 \times 10^5 \quad (95)$$

E. Computation of base of three digits number of power of base 5

In the expansion of $(xyz)^5$ the kif matrix of the expansion of trinomial expression of power of 5 is obtained as follow. Each term of the matrix is generated and the all the terms for each row is added together.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 500 \\ 410 \\ 320 + 401 \\ 230 + 311 \\ 140 + 221 + 302 \\ 050 + 131 + 212 \\ 041 + 122 + 203 \\ 032 + 113 \\ 023 + 104 \\ 014 \\ 005 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(xyz)^5 = \begin{bmatrix} {}_{5,0,0}^5C x^5 y^0 z^0 \\ {}_{4,1,0}^5C x^4 y^1 z^0 \\ {}_{3,2,0}^5C x^3 y^2 z^0 + {}_{4,0,1}^5C x^4 y^0 z^1 \\ {}_{2,3,0}^5C x^2 y^3 z^0 + {}_{1,0,1}^5C x^3 y^1 z^1 \\ {}_{1,4,0}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 + {}_{0,1,4}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 + {}_{0,1,4}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 \\ {}_{0,5,0}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 + {}_{0,1,4}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 + {}_{0,1,4}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 \\ {}_{0,2,3}^5C x^0 y^2 z^3 + {}_{1,0,4}^5C x^1 y^0 z^4 \\ {}_{0,1,4}^5C x^0 y^1 z^4 \\ {}_{0,0,5}^5C x^0 y^0 z^5 \end{bmatrix}$$

The single column matrix obtained is further simplified to achieve the final answer.

Illustration

Evaluate the following using kif matrix approach

- [i] $(420)^5$ [ii] $(321)^4$

Solution

- [i] $(420)^5$

The kifilideen matrix to solve the expression is given as

$$\begin{bmatrix} 500 \\ 410 \\ 320 + 401 \\ 230 + 311 \\ 140 + 221 + 302 \\ 050 + 131 + 212 \\ 041 + 122 + 203 \\ 032 + 113 \\ 023 + 104 \\ 014 \\ 005 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, we have

$$(420)^5 = \begin{bmatrix} {}_{5,0,0}C 4^5 2^0 0^0 \\ {}_{4,1,0}C 4^4 2^1 0^0 \\ {}_{3,2,0}C 4^3 2^2 0^0 + {}_{4,0,1}C 4^4 2^0 0^1 \\ {}_{2,3,0}C 4^2 2^3 0^0 + {}_{3,1,1}C 4^3 2^1 0^1 \\ {}_{1,4,0}C 4^1 2^4 0^0 + {}_{2,2,1}C 4^2 2^2 0^1 + {}_{3,0,2}C 4^3 2^0 0^2 \\ {}_{0,5,0}C 4^0 2^5 0^0 + {}_{1,3,1}C 4^1 2^3 0^1 + {}_{2,1,2}C 4^2 2^1 0^2 \\ {}_{0,4,1}C 4^0 2^4 0^1 + {}_{1,2,2}C 4^1 2^2 0^2 + {}_{2,0,3}C 4^2 2^0 0^3 \\ {}_{0,3,2}C 4^0 2^3 0^2 + {}_{1,1,3}C 4^1 2^1 0^3 \\ {}_{0,2,3}C 4^0 2^2 0^3 + {}_{1,0,4}C 4^1 2^0 0^4 \\ {}_{0,1,4}C 4^0 2^1 0^4 \\ {}_{0,0,5}C 4^0 2^0 0^5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (96)$$

$$(420)^5 = \begin{bmatrix} 1024 \\ 2560 \\ 2560 \\ 1280 \\ 320 \\ 32 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (97)$$

1024	2560	2560	1280	320	32	0	0	0	0	0
	282	↑	269	↑	131	↑	32	↑	3	

1306	9	1	2	3	2	0	0	0	0	0
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$$(420)^5 = 13069123200000 \text{ or } 1.30691232 \times 10^{13} \quad (98) \quad \text{The kifilideen matrix to solve the expression is given as}$$

[ii] $(321)^4$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 400 \\ 310 \\ 220 + 301 \\ 130 + 211 \\ 040 + 121 + 202 \\ 031 + 112 \\ 022 + 103 \\ 013 \\ 004 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}_{4,0,0}C 3^4 2^0 1^0 \\ {}_{3,1,0}C 3^3 2^1 1^0 \\ {}_{2,2,0}C 3^2 2^2 1^0 + {}_{3,0,1}C 3^3 2^0 1^1 \\ {}_{1,3,0}C 3^1 2^3 1^0 + {}_{2,1,1}C 3^2 2^1 1^1 \\ {}_{0,4,0}C 3^0 2^4 1^0 + {}_{1,2,1}C 3^1 2^2 1^1 + {}_{2,0,2}C 3^2 2^0 1^2 \\ {}_{0,3,1}C 3^0 2^3 1^1 + {}_{1,1,2}C 3^1 2^1 1^2 \\ {}_{0,2,2}C 3^0 2^2 1^2 + {}_{1,0,3}C 3^1 2^0 1^3 \\ {}_{0,1,3}C 3^0 2^1 1^3 \\ {}_{0,0,4}C 3^0 2^0 1^4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(321)^4 = \begin{bmatrix} 81 \\ 216 \\ 216 + 108 \\ 96 + 216 \\ 16 + 144 + 54 \\ 32 + 72 \\ 24 + 12 \\ 8 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 81 \\ 216 \\ 324 \\ 312 \\ 214 \\ 104 \\ 36 \\ 8 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (99)$$

$(321)^5 = 10617447681$ or $1.0617447681 \times 10^{10}$ (100)

The kifilideen matrix to solve the expression is given has

Expand the following using kif matrix approach

[i] $[902]^2 + [141]^2$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 200 \\ 110 \\ 020 + 101 \\ 011 \\ 002 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solution

So, we have

$$[902]^2 + [141]^2 = \begin{bmatrix} {}_{2,0,0}^2C 9^2 0^0 2^0 \\ {}_{1,1,0}^2C 9^1 0^1 2^0 \\ {}_{0,2,0}^2C 9^0 0^2 2^0 + {}_{1,0,1}^2C 9^1 0^0 2^1 \\ {}_{0,1,1}^2C 9^0 0^1 2^1 \\ {}_{0,0,2}^2C 9^0 0^0 2^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} {}_{2,0,0}^2C 1^2 4^0 1^0 \\ {}_{1,1,0}^2C 1^1 4^1 1^0 \\ {}_{0,2,0}^2C 1^0 4^2 1^0 + {}_{1,0,1}^2C 1^1 4^0 1^1 \\ {}_{0,1,1}^2C 1^0 4^1 1^1 \\ {}_{0,0,2}^2C 1^0 4^0 1^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (101)$$

$$[902]^2 + [141]^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 81 \\ 0 \\ 0 + 36 \\ 0 \\ 4 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 8 \\ 16 + 2 \\ 8 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 82 \\ 8 \\ 54 \\ 8 \\ 5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (102)$$

82	8	54	8	5
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 5

83	3	4	8	5
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$$[902]^2 + [141]^2 = 851545 \text{ or } 8.51545 \times 10^5 \quad (103)$$

III. DISCUSSION

The kif matrix approach in solving the trinomial expression of power n does not involve the repeated multiplication of figure unlike the long multiplication approach. This eliminates the boring nature of using binomial theorem to expand trinomial of power n.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study utilized kifilideen trinomial theorem based on matrix approach in computation of the power of base of tri-digits number. This method adopts and employs kif matrix approach in generating the power combination required in the evaluation. This method would help to eliminate humdrum nature and inconvenient of using binomial theorem in expanding trinomial expression of any power.

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